

See, Touch, Feel: Theorising Twitter/X Images for Diplomacy

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Social media images are central to the practice of digital diplomacy. Some of the most contentious political engagements involve digital images designed to challenge or reaffirm the national identity of key political players. Yet the role of touch in conditioning how social media images are seen is curiously absent from International Relations analyses of the visual politics of digital diplomacy. We know far too little about this phenomenon. This article seeks to contribute to the study of images in global politics by developing a tripartite theorisation of how the visual, tactile and emotional intersect to mediate how Twitter images are seen within the practice of digital diplomacy. The article pays attention to the tactile experience of using Twitter, bridging the gap between seeing social media images as visual objects and the affective resonance these images have as a marker of political power. I argue that touch acts as a conduit between the embodied, material and visual to produces an affective encounter that contributes to how users feel about Twitter images. The intertextuality of the visual, tactile and emotional dynamics of Twitter images are important elements of visual social media practices sustaining the strategic representation of identity. This framework allows me to build a theoretically grounded skillful speculation as to how digital diplomacy crisis events such as the China-Australia Twitter spat unfold and resonate beyond the digital.

Keywords: Twitter/X, visual politics, emotion, digital diplomacy

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Introduction

In late 2020, amidst deteriorating Australia-China relations that included Chinese trade sanctions on Australian exports such as wine, beef, and barley in response to Australia calling for a global public inquiry into the origins of the coronavirus, Chinese Foreign Ministry spokesperson Zhao Lijian tweeted a doctored image of an Australian soldier violently assaulting an Afghan child. The image was captioned with the statement ‘Shocked by murder of Afghan prisoners & civilians by Australian soldiers. We strongly condemn such acts, & call for holding them accountable’. This image triggered an almost immediate response from Australian Prime Minister Scott Morrison, who called a press conference two hours later to demand an apology from Beijing over an act he said severely diminished the reputation of China. Following the retort from foreign ministry spokesperson Hua Chunying that it was only Australia who should be ashamed, Beijing effectively severed diplomatic ties with Australia. Within the context of the already fragile China-Australia relations, the strength of the reaction by Morrison was surprising. What was so unique about this image, that an Australian political leader felt it necessary to call out and risk further inflaming regional tensions between Australia and China?

Hundreds of millions of images are posted online every minute. Each time we scroll through social media we are exposed to hundreds of images at any one time. Some of the most contentious political engagements involve images designed to challenge or reaffirm the identity of key political players. Just like everyday people, political leaders and diplomats are exposed to incredible amounts of visual information to process and assess, with the speed of digital communication blurring our online and off-line social lives.¹ What makes social media images so powerful, however, is the overlap of visual, tactile and emotional dynamics. These elements taken together form a composite of visual social media practices sustaining the strategic representation of identity as part of diplomatic practice. Images play a central role in sustaining or challenging identity narratives: more importantly, digital platforms such as Twitter – now rebranded as X – condition how these images are seen and emotionally responded to.²

This article seeks to contribute to the study of images in global politics by examining the how visual, tactile and emotional dynamics are bundled together when Twitter users interact with the platform via their smartphone. The article pays particular attention to the tactile experience of

¹ L.J. Shepherd, ‘Aesthetics, ethics, and visual research in the digital age: “Undone in the face of the otter”’, *Millennium* 45:2(2017), p. 217.

² Following Møller et al (2024) and Harris & Lin-Greenberg (2024), I use ‘Twitter’ throughout the article as the events referred to in the article occurred prior to the platform’s rebranding, and many scholars and policymakers continue to refer to the platform by its original name.

using Twitter, bridging the gap between seeing social media images as visual objects and the affective resonance these images have as a marker of political power. It demonstrates how the intertextuality of seeing a Twitter image (See), physically engaging with it (Touch), and emotionally responding to it (Feel), are delineated yet interrelated and ultimately integrated in the user experience of Twitter. These senses work together to produce a different kind of affective space within which identity narratives are built and challenged. In doing so, this article makes a further contribution to work that situates the digital at the heart of global politics, and research examining the political intersection of technology and power. It theorises how diplomatic practitioners and political leaders, much like everyday users, interact with social media platforms such as Twitter via this visual, haptic and emotional bundling. Following Merje Kuus' call for greater methodological relaxation,³ this framework allows me to build a theoretically grounded skillful speculation as to how digital diplomacy crisis events such as the China-Australia Twitter spat unfold and resonate, when we as researchers do not have direct access to practitioners or political leaders during those moments in time.

Social media has greatly influenced practices around image production, circulation and consumption,⁴ transforming how diplomats represent their nations and engage with foreign publics. While the positive impact is well documented, with greater speed and access to information contributing to a better understanding of what foreign publics need or desire, the damaging effects of social media on diplomacy are also clear.⁵ Diplomats are under immense pressure to respond immediately to tweets, with limited time to process information.⁶ The rise of digital disinformation, the deliberate spread of text and image-based information online to deceive and mislead, further complicates diplomats' capacity to assess and respond to events as they unfold.⁷ The ease with which images can go 'viral'—reaching millions of people within the space of a few hours—introduces a complex dynamic to questions regarding the political power of

³ M. Kuus, 'Bureaucratic Sociability, or the Missing Eighty Percent of Effectiveness: The Case of Diplomacy', *Geopolitics* 28:1 (2023): 174-195.

⁴ M. MacKenzie, 'Why do soldiers swap illicit pictures? How a visual discourse analysis illuminates military band of brother culture', *Security dialogue* 51:4 (2020), p. 4, 10.

⁵ P. Barberá P and T. Zeitzoff, 'The new public address system: why do world leaders adopt social media?', *International Studies Quarterly* 62:1 (2018), pp. 121-130; J. Burgess and A. Bruns, '(Not) the X election: the dynamics of the# ausvotes conversation in relation to the Australian media ecology', *Journalism Practice* 6:3 (2012), pp. 384-402.

⁶ C. Duncombe, 'The politics of Twitter: emotions and the power of social media', *International Political Sociology* 13:4 (2019), pp. 409-429.

⁷ C. Bjola and J. Pamment, eds. *Countering online propaganda and extremism: The dark side of digital diplomacy* (Routledge, 2018); Y. Golovchenko, M. Hartmann, and R. Adler-Nissen, 'State, media and civil society in the information warfare over Ukraine: citizen curators of digital disinformation', *International Affairs* 94:5 (2018): 975-994.

images.⁸ States frequently ‘troll’ others by using images to undermine claims to identity and political authority, such as with the example of the tweet by Zhou Lijian.⁹ Research in IR that takes seriously how technological affordances can facilitate transformative change in diplomacy has demonstrated how diplomatic actors both embrace or resist social media as part of diplomatic practice.¹⁰ Diplomats and political leaders are therefore not immune to the effects of social media platforms such as Twitter: a key example is former US President Donald Trump, who used Twitter to conduct foreign policy until his Twitter ban following the January 6 riots in 2021. Even political leaders without Twitter profiles such as former German Chancellor Angela Merkel – who deployed Instagram by comparison – were forced to respond to Trump’s tweets, as that was the ‘frequency’ he was communicating in.¹¹ Social media platforms such as Twitter have ‘virtually displaced all small moments of downtime’ for diplomats; even if they find the constant connection annoying, they recognize the importance of ‘one foot’ being anchored in their offline space with ‘perhaps one or two toes online’.¹² Yet we still do not know enough about how social media images have implications for offline political engagement.¹³

This paper contributes a phenomenological story of the body, in part to counter what Anna Leander calls ‘the illusion of disembodied politics, including the fetishization of technology and technological solutions’ to political conflicts.¹⁴ For instance, work on strategic narratives and public diplomacy increasingly pays attention to social media as the forums through which states tell stories about themselves to international audiences. Yet understanding how touch functions as

⁸ H. Berents, ‘Politics, policy-making and the presence of images of suffering children’, *International Affairs* 96:3 (2020), pp. 593-608; G. Schlag, ‘Moving images and the politics of pity: a multilevel approach to the interpretation of images and emotions’, in Clément M and Sanger E (eds) *Researching emotions in international relations* (Basingstoke: Palgrave, 2018).

⁹ R. Adler-Nissen and A. Tsinovoi, ‘International misrecognition: The politics of humour and national identity in Israel’s public diplomacy’, *European Journal of International Relations* 25:1 (2019), pp. 3-29; R. Crilley and P.N. Chatterje-Dood, ‘From Russia with lols: Humour, RT, and the legitimation of Russian foreign policy’, *Global Society* 35:2(2021), pp. 269-288.

¹⁰ R. Adler-Nissen and A. Drieschova, ‘Track-change diplomacy: Technology, affordances, and the practice of international negotiations’, *International Studies Quarterly* (2019); A. Danielson and E. Hedling, ‘Visual diplomacy in virtual summitry: Status signalling during the coronavirus crisis’, *Review of International Studies* 48:2(2022), pp.243-261; I. Manor, *The digitalization of public diplomacy* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2019); R. Adler-Nissen and K.A. Eggeling, ‘Blended diplomacy: The entanglement and contestation of digital technologies in everyday diplomatic practice’, *European Journal of International Relations* 28:3 (2022), pp. 640-666.

¹¹ Adler-Nissen and Eggeling, ‘Blended diplomacy’, p. 655.

¹² Adler-Nissen and K.A. Eggeling, ‘Blended diplomacy’, p. 644, 647.

¹³ Duncombe, ‘The politics of Twitter’; C. Zhang, ‘Contested disaster nationalism in the digital age: Emotional registers and geopolitical imaginaries in COVID-19 narratives on Chinese social media’, *Review of International Studies* 48:2(2022), pp. 219-242.

¹⁴ A. Leander, ‘Locating (new) materialist characters and processes in global governance’, *International Theory* 13(2021), p. 161; M. Merlau-Ponty, *The visible and the invisible, followed by working notes* (Evanston: Northwestern University Press, 1968).

part of the experience of seeing digital images is overlooked in favour of discursive and visual analysis.¹⁵ Research theorizing potential links between visual representations and policy discourse analyses images such as photographs from news articles, comics or posters to detail the possible connections between one or more images and shifts in, strengthening of, or challenges to policy outcomes.¹⁶ The forms through which these images circulate is given less attention, including what role the haptic experience of digital platforms might play in the intensification of securitizing policy discourses. More recently, studies have gone further in the examination of the intersection of social media and images, but these do not foreground the function of touch in the constitution of visuals as political.¹⁷

The article proceeds in three steps: first, I explore work at the intersection of visual politics and diplomacy studies to highlight the absence of tactility in these literatures, and to make the case for including the role of touch in conceptualizing the affective dimensions of Twitter images. I focus on Twitter because it has remained the most accepted platform globally for political leaders and diplomats, with 368 million active users a month, the vast majority of whom access the platform via their smartphone. Despite the global popularity of other public-facing social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram, which are themselves utilized by governments for

¹⁵ E. Zhukova, M.R. Sundström, and O. Elgström, 'Feminist foreign policies (FFPs) as strategic narratives: Norm translation in Sweden, Canada, France, and Mexico', *Review of international studies* 48:1(2022), pp. 195-216; A. Miskimmon and B. O'Loughlin, 'The visual politics of the 2015 Iran deal: narrative, image and verification', *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 33:5 (2020), pp. 778-798; A. Miskimmon, B. O'loughlin and L. Roselle, *Strategic narratives: Communication power and the new world order* (UK: Routledge., 2014); J. Dickinson, 'Visualising the foreign and the domestic in diaspora diplomacy: images and the online politics of recognition in# givingtoindia', *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 33:5 (2020), pp. 752-777; A. Kopper, 'The use of humour in diplomatic tweets: The affiliative potential of ridicule', *Cooperation and Conflict* 56:3(2021), pp. 309-327; A.A. Jamal, R.O. Keohane, D. Romney and D. Tingley, 'Anti-Americanism and anti-interventionism in Arabic X discourses', *Perspectives on Politics* 13:1 (2015), pp. 55-73; R. Crilly, M. Gillespie and A. Willis, 'Tweeting the Russian revolution: RT's# 1917LIVE and social media re-enactments as public diplomacy', *European journal of cultural studies* 23:3(2020), pp. 354-373.

¹⁶ E. Hutchison, 'A global politics of pity? Disaster imagery and the emotional construction of solidarity after the 2004 Asian tsunami', *International Political Sociology* 8:1(2014), pp. 1-19; A. Adler-Nissen, K.E. Andersen and L. Hansen, 'Images, emotions, and international politics: the death of Alan Kurdi', *Review of International Studies* 46:1(2020), pp. 75-95; G. Karavas, 'How images frame China's role in African development', *International Affairs* 96:3(2020), pp. 667-690; F.C. Windfeld, M.H. Hvithamar, and L. Hansen, 'Gothic visibilities and International Relations: Uncanny icons, critical comics, and the politics of abjection in Aleppo', *Review of International Studies* (2023), pp. 1-32; D. Cooper-Cunningham, 'Seeing (in) security, gender and silencing: Posters in and about the British women's suffrage movement', *International Feminist Journal of Politics* 21:3(2019), pp. 383-408; D. Cooper-Cunningham, 'Drawing fear of difference: Race, gender, and national identity in Ms. Marvel comics', *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* 48:2 (2020), pp. 165-197; M. Loken, 'Both needed and threatened': Armed mothers in militant visuals', *Security Dialogue* 52:1(2021), pp. 21-44.

¹⁷ N. Robinson and M. Schulzke, 'Visualizing war? Towards a visual analysis of videogames and social media', *Perspectives on Politics* 14:4(2016), pp. 995-1010; MacKenzie, 'Why do soldiers swap illicit pictures?'; H. Malmvig, 'Jesting international politics: The productive power and limitations of humorous practices in an age of entertainment politics', *Review of International Studies* (2022): 1-22.; U. Baspehlivan, 'Theorising the memescape: The spatial politics of Internet memes', *Review of International Studies* (2023): 1-23; Zhang, 'Contested disaster nationalism in the digital age'; Dickinson, 'Visualising the foreign and the domestic in diaspora diplomacy'; William A. Callahan, *Sensible Politics: Visualizing International Relations* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2020); K. Aggestam, A. Bergman Rosamond and E. Hedling, 'Digital norm contestation and feminist foreign policy', *International Studies Perspectives* (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1093/isp/ekad017>

political communication, Twitter – design explicitly as a smartphone application – has nevertheless remained the central technological tool in diplomacy precisely because of the nature of the communication it facilitates: short, direct and public messages that can both represent and provoke strong emotional reactions from other users, leading to large-scale debates that become integrated into offline political outcomes.¹⁸ As such, ‘personal and collective emotional components become entangled in ways that mean state-to-state relations can be profoundly affected by the individual-centric feelings of diplomats’.¹⁹ This is particularly challenging for diplomats and political leaders as they navigate social media interactions, expending significant emotional labour to restrain their emotional responses as part of positive communication practices signifying enactment of the ‘good diplomat’ role.²⁰ The need for constant performance online, and the kinds of performances this entails – tweets signifying emotional registers of anger or hostility or general negativity travel further than ones that do not – often conflict directly with the comportment of their daily professional roles.²¹

Second, I introduce a theorisation of how user experience of social media images is shaped, exploring the role of the visual (See), tactile (Touch) and emotion (Feel) that bundles together in a multisensorial user interaction with Twitter images. I focus on smartphones, rather than tablets, desktop computers or laptops, because of the intimate relationship users have with their smartphones: the intimacy of the body (holding the smartphone, using the thumb to scroll through social media timelines), alongside the material hardware, software and digital platform affordances, is central to the circulation and consumption of digital images.²² Twitter images have, therefore, a different kind of potential to evoke or represent emotions, because these images become an extension of the hand, rendering any barrier between online and offline worlds obsolete through this force of movement. I show how the intersection of seeing and touching Twitter images can draw the user into a space beyond themselves, whereby the visual frames, and is framed by, an emotional experience connecting an individual to a broader collectivity. Finally, I use the Australia-China Twitter image as a descriptive study to illustrate how the see-touch-feel framework might

¹⁸ For a discussion of the different emotional logics across social media platforms such as X/Twitter, Facebook and Instagram, see: C. Duncombe, ‘Social media and the visibility of horrific violence’, *International Affairs* 96(2020): pp. 609-629.

¹⁹ B. Keys and C. Yorke, ‘Personal and political emotions in the mind of the diplomat’, *Political Psychology* 40:6 (2019): pp. 1235-1249.

²⁰ E. Hedling, ‘Emotional labour in digital diplomacy: perceptions and challenges for European diplomats’, *Emotions and Society* 5:1 (2023): pp. 29-47.

²¹ Hedling, ‘Emotional labour in digital diplomacy’.

²² For a discussion of how smartphones are both embedded in and embed global conflict, see J. Norman, M. Ford and S.M. Cold-Ravnkilde, ‘The crisis in the palm of our hand’, *International Affairs* 100:4 (2024): pp. 1361–1379.

offer a way to think through the creation and consumption of Twitter images and how this shapes political possibilities. There are two reproductions of the image in this section of the paper (pp. 27 and 30), which readers may find disturbing.

Visualising Twitter in Digital Diplomacy

What role do images play in digital diplomacy? Here, I examine the overlap between the visual and the digital as the first step in demonstrating the centrality of touch as constituting how these images are seen and the spaces within which they circulate. I employ perspectives from media and communication studies, sociology, visual cultures and international relations to illustrate the aesthetic practices that shape the visual conditions of Twitter, which in turn overlap with the performative practices of diplomacy. What is missing from these accounts, I suggest, is an understanding of how the tactile engagement with Twitter images mobilizes emotional conditions via the online space of Twitter itself, which adds to the emotional resonance of images as they circulate first online then offline.

Images have long been recognized as powerful artefacts in global politics. Their narrative power emerges from their capacity to tell us (or not) something about international relations, and the consequent impact this has on processes of global politics.²³ Images both reflect and engender visual landscapes that ‘promote very specific interpretations of the depicted issue’,²⁴ which in turn have become integral parts of the visualization of war and conflict.²⁵ Yet the polysemic nature of images means there is no definitive or essential message they evoke: rather, the relationship between emotions and images renders certain images more or less capable of invoking emotions at given points in time.²⁶ Rebecca Adler-Nissen, Katrine Emilie Andersen and Lene Hansen use the example of photographs of Alan Kurdi, a three-year-old Syrian-Kurdish boy who drowned in September 2015 to demonstrate how different meanings attributed to images emerge through the

²³ MacKenzie, ‘Why do soldiers swap illicit pictures?’, p. 341; Loken ‘Both needed and threatened’, p. 22; E. Cusumano, ‘Private military and security companies logos: Between camouflaging and corporate socialization’, *Security Dialogue* 52:2 (2021), pp. 135-155; G. Rose, *Visual methodologies: An introduction to the interpretation of visual materials* (Sage: London), 2016;

²⁴ S.J. Baele, K. A. Boyd and T.G. Coan, ‘Lethal images: Analyzing extremist visual propaganda from ISIS and Beyond’, *Journal of Global Security Studies* 5:4 (2020), pp. 634-657, p. 636.

²⁵ M. Makhortykh and M. Sydorova, ‘Social media and visual framing of the conflict in Eastern Ukraine’, *Media, War and Conflict* 10:3 (2017), pp. 359-381.

²⁶ Adler-Nissen, Andersen and Hansen, ‘Images, emotions and international politics’, p. 78; R. Bleiker, ‘Pluralist methods for visual global politics’, *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* 43:3 (2015), p. 876; L. Hansen, ‘Theorizing the image for security studies: Visual securitization and the Muhammad Cartoon Crisis’, *European Journal of International Relations* 17:1 (2011), pp. 51-74.

performance and constitution of discourse. They introduce the concept of ‘emotional bundling’ to theorize how an array of emotions can intermingle and overlap via discourse to constitute a singular emotional response, which may (or may not) influence policy change or maintenance.²⁷ What we see, how we see it, and how we feel about it, is therefore not a direct and staid relationship, but ‘exists at the intersection between the gaze and the subject/object of representation’.²⁸ It is important to note that images themselves do not necessarily convey or produce new information about key political events: anchoring is a significant element that shapes their meaning.²⁹ What makes images so powerful, and so deeply embedded in the epistemological terrain of politics, is their ability to shift discourse on a particular issue away from abstract numbers and statistics to something knowable, oftentimes ‘to an identifiable human with a face, a body and a life story’.³⁰ Visuals become ‘understandable’ through the discursive framing of how or why particular events are occurring.³¹ Texts provide meaning to the image – tweets, news articles or policy statements help to constitute a particular discursive reading of an image that attributes particular meaning to it, beyond the immediate photograph, meme or video. The social significance of an image derives from its interpretation, which is fundamentally embedded in a linguistic message that signals how or why it is so important.³²

While images are key vehicles for communication, social media images occupy a particularly prominent place within the broader visually oriented media ecosystem. Social media facilitates the circulation of both moving and still images that contour how ‘reality’ is represented and understood, which in turn both opens up and restricts political imaginaries. This has had a particularly profound effect on the practice of diplomacy, with the past decade notable for the ‘mass migration of MFAs and diplomats to social media sites’ as part of the turn towards digital diplomacy practice.³³ Political leaders, diplomats and MFA representatives alike have increasingly adopted Twitter as a key part of daily information-sharing behaviour. The perspective that digital diplomacy is ‘experimental and thus characterized by high degrees of risk-taking’³⁴ relies on what

²⁷ Adler-Nissen, Andersen and Hansen, ‘Images, emotions and international politics’, p. 94.

²⁸ C. Achilleos-Sarll, “‘Seeing’ the Women, Peace and Security agenda: Visual (re)productions of WPS in UK government national action plans’, *International Affairs* 96:6 (2020), pp. 1643-1663, p. 1648.

²⁹ Adler-Nissen, Andersen and Hansen, ‘Images, emotions, and international politics’, p. 76.

³⁰ Adler-Nissen, Andersen and Hansen, ‘Images, emotions, and international politics’, p. 76.

³¹ Hansen, ‘Theorizing the image for security studies’.

³² Adler-Nissen, Andersen and Hansen, ‘Images, emotions, and international politics’, p. 79.

³³ I. Manor and R. Crilley, ‘Visually framing the Gaza War of 2014: The Israel Ministry of Foreign Affairs on X’, *Media, War and Conflict* 11:4 (2018), pp. 369-391, p. 372.

³⁴ Danielson and Hedling, ‘Visual diplomacy in virtual summitry’, p. 1604.

Van Dijck and Poell conceptualise as social media logic,³⁵ wherein the intersection of programmability, popularity, connectivity and datafication has led to a ‘post-protocol world of diplomacy in which imagery is used by multiple actors, operating at multiple levels, and pursuing multiple objectives’.³⁶

What must not be overlooked in considerations of how social media platforms technologically mediate the social and the political, therefore, is the role of images in this process. Tweeting images is a key part of information-sharing behaviour within digital diplomacy practice: images are tied to emotions, and in an ‘increasingly “cluttered media landscape competing for eyeballs”’ people are far more likely to share information – through likes, retweets, or retweets with comments – if what they are seeing generates an affective or emotional reactions.³⁷ For instance, when an Irish diplomat tweeted a picture of a puddle in the shape of Ireland on the pavement outside the building of Ireland’s Permanent Representation to the European Union, it quickly became the PERMREP’s most retweeted post, and possibly the most liked tweet of any foreign ministry in Brussels.³⁸ Other Twitter users responded with their own ‘reminders of home’, photos of chicken nuggets, prawn crackers and water condensation on pub tables.³⁹ Twitter images can act as powerful visual nodes that frame global public engagement with political issues and events, precisely because the extreme levels of circulation expose millions of people to key images at any one time.

Within studies on digital diplomacy, several scholars have explored the role of Twitter images in practices of public diplomacy and strategic narrative construction. Drawing on media framing theory introduced by Robert Entman to explore how the Israel Ministry of Foreign Affairs used Twitter to visually frame the 2014 Gaza War, Ilan Manor and Rhys Crilley show how images resonate with frames designed to legitimize actions during times of conflict, arguing that images are therefore a vital component of contemporary digital diplomacy and framing in war and conflict. In terms of communication towards alignment and peace-making, Alister Miskimmon and Ben

³⁵ Van Dijck and T. Poell, ‘Understanding social media logic’, *Media and communication* 1:1(2013), pp. 2-14.

³⁶ C.M. Constantinou, ‘Visual diplomacy: Reflections on diplomatic spectacle and cinematic thinking’, *The Hague Journal of Diplomacy* 13(2018), pp. 387-409, p. 389-390.

³⁷ M. Lalancette and V. Raynauld, ‘The power of political image: Justin Trudeau, Instagram, and celebrity politics’, *American Behavioral Scientist* 63:7(2019), p. 890; T-A Hoang, W. Cohen, E-P Lim, D. Pierce, and D. Redlawsk, ‘Politics, sharing and emotion in microblogs’, *Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining* (2013), p. 283; for an analysis of the racial and gendered sharing affordances of social media see L. Nakamura, “‘I WILL Do EVERYthing that I am asked’”: Scambaiting, digital show-space and the racial violence of social media’, *Journal of Visual Culture* 13(2014): pp. 257-274.

³⁸ E. Beswick, ‘Puddle shape of Irish island spotted in Brussels street’, *EuroNews.com*, available at {<https://www.euronews.com/2018/12/06/puddle-shape-of-irish-ireland-spotted-in-brussels-street>}, accessed 15 June 2023; Adler-Nissen and Eggeling, ‘Blended diplomacy’, p. 649.

³⁹ Beswick, ‘Puddle shape of Irish island’.

O'Loughlin explore the visual politics of the 2015 Iran nuclear deal to show how Iranian and US diplomats utilized Twitter images as part of a coordinated strategic narrative campaign resulting in the successful implementation of the deal.⁴⁰ Jen Dickinson deploys a semiotic approach to analyse both tweets and Facebook posts of the India Development Foundation of Overseas Indian (IDF-OI) as part of diaspora diplomacy practice, demonstrating how Twitter and Facebook images worked together to legitimize particular representations of the Indian diaspora and championed those with the most structural, economic and cultural capital.⁴¹

Taken together, these interventions show that Twitter images – photographs, cartoons, memes, GIFs, videos – have a role to play in the relational production of power through the visual framing of events and experiences imaged over Twitter as provoking or representing emotions.⁴² Regimes of visual representation condition, reproduce and shape how we comprehend politics. Such regimes normalise representational practices and provide opportunities for them to resonate within broader discourses as ‘authoritative, truthful, and/or emotively powerful’.⁴³ They provide order to the way we see and perceive reality; our understandings of security, development, peace and conflict are embedded within visual frameworks that legitimize dominant approaches to political issues.⁴⁴ Digital technology is central to the circulation of images: how images are shared using certain platforms enables practices of seeing, sensing and witnessing political phenomena.⁴⁵ The intersection of the visual and material contribute to how the politics of conflict and peace are seen and understood.⁴⁶

⁴⁰ A. Miskimmon and B. O'Loughlin, 'The visual politics of the 2015 Iran deal: Narrative, image and verification', *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 33:5 (2020), pp. 778-798.

⁴¹ Dickinson, 'Visualising the foreign and the domestic in diaspora diplomacy'.

⁴² J.E. Hopke and L.E. Hestres, 'Visualizing the Paris climate talks on X: Media and climate stakeholder visual social media during COP21', *Social Media+ Society* 4:3(2018), p. 4.

⁴³ K. Grayson K and J. Mawdsley, 'Scopic regimes and the visual turn in International Relations: Seeing world politics through the drone', *European Journal of International Relations* 25:2 (2019), pp. 431-457; Karavas, 'How images frame China's role in African development'; M. Jay, 'Scopic regimes of modernity', in H. Foster (ed.) *Vision and Visuality* (New York, NY: New Press, 1988), pp. 3–23; A. Jerrems, 'The politics of neighbouring: assembly politics, urban citizenship and regimes of visibility in post-crisis Madrid', *Citizenship Studies* 24:8 (2020), pp. 1047-1065.

⁴⁴ M. Crone, 'It's a man's world: carnal spectatorship and dissonant masculinities in Islamic State videos', *International Affairs* 96:3(2020), pp. 573-591; Grayson and Mawdsley, 'Scopic regimes and the visual turn in International Relations'; Karavas, 'How images frame China's role in African development'.

⁴⁵ D. Rothe, C. Fröhlich and J.M. Rodriguez Lopez, 'Digital Humanitarianism and the Visual Politics of the Refugee Camp: (Un) Seeing Control', *International Political Sociology* 15:1(2021), pp. 41-62; Grayson and Mawdsley, 'Scopic regimes and the visual turn in International Relations'.

⁴⁶ J. Tidy, 'Visual regimes and the politics of war experience: Rewriting war "from above" in WikiLeaks "Collateral Murder"', *Review of international studies* 431(2017), pp. 95-111; D. Rothe and D. Shim, 'Sensing the ground: On the global politics of satellite-based activism', *Review of International Studies* 44:3(2018), pp. 414; Rothe, Fröhlich and Rodriguez Lopez, 'Digital Humanitarianism and the Visual Politics of the Refugee Camp'; E. Serafinelli and L.A. O'Hagan, 'Drone views: a multimodal ethnographic perspective', *Visual Communication* (2022): 14703572211065093; E.

What is missing in these accounts, I suggest, is an understanding of how emotional conditions are mobilised in relation to images circulating on Twitter via the physical interaction of touch between user, interface and image. If images are ‘not singular artefacts that “sit still” on gallery walls or other fixed locations’, they must necessarily require other senses to experience and identify, and consequently interpret, them.⁴⁷ Photos, videos, memes, or any other visual artefact do not just appear online – they require a physical interaction drawing on algorithms, the interface of the social media platform, and the body to become constituted as a digital image made visible to platform users and viewers both online and offline.

The tactile nature of seeing Twitter images is intimately intertwined with the social and political processes that have transformed communication practices so profoundly. As a technological space, Twitter has the capacity to shape the social interactions that occur online – the emotional conditions of Twitter can alter the material context of social interaction, mediating how we receive and perceive information.⁴⁸ The entanglement of virtual interface, material technology and the body allows for the ‘sense-making of oneself and co-present others as body subjects’ that in turn produce other ‘entangled modes of relatedness and possibilities of connection involved in new media processes’.⁴⁹ If smartphones and their interfaces are integral to the rhythms of the domestic sphere, so too are they to the public sphere of high politics.⁵⁰ Digital diplomacy practices are thus conditioned through tactile and technologically mediated forms of emotions, which facilitate collective feelings of community among digital networked publics.

See-Touch-Feel: Introducing Touch to Theorising Twitter Images

To fully appreciate what social media images can do, and how they can create affective communities of sense – drawing people together and shaping political identities through visceral

Archambault and Y. Veilleux-Lepage, ‘Drone imagery in Islamic State propaganda: flying like a state’, *International Affairs* 96:4(2020), pp. 955-973.

⁴⁷ MacKenzie, ‘Why do soldiers swap illicit pictures?’, p.4; S. Pink, ‘Sensory digital photography: rethinking ‘moving’ and the image’, *Visual Studies* 26 (2011), pp. 4-13.

⁴⁸ J. Van Dijck and T. Poell, ‘Understanding social media logic’, *Media and communication* 1:1(2013), pp. 2-14; A.G. Ross, *Mixed emotions: Beyond fear and hatred in international conflict* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013); Duncombe, ‘The politics of Twitter’.

⁴⁹ L. J. Mertens, ‘Being-in-touch: The (im)possibilities of communicative and tactile connection in online experiences’, *New Media & Society* 0:0 (2023).

⁵⁰ I. Richardson and L. Hjorth, ‘Mobile media, domestic play and haptic ethnography’, *New Media & Society*, 19:10 (2017), pp. 1653-1667.

response to what they see⁵¹ – we need to pay attention not just to the visual – what the images depict or signify – but also to the role of touch as constituting how these images are seen and the spaces within which they circulate. Touch is an incredibly important part of Twitter as a visual experience: users can touch their smartphone screen or their computer mouse or tracker to scroll through tweets on their homepage. In doing so any image can be touched, opened or scrolled past, but never hidden. Twitter images are therefore both optical and tactile: the digital nature of Twitter images means ‘they are as much about multisensory feelings as they are about seeing’.⁵² While images in a user’s Twitter feed (what they see on their homepage) are still compressed thumbnails that are algorithmically cropped to enable the image to fit within a tweet, the full, uncompressed image appears once the user selects and clicks through the tweet and its connected image.⁵³

Building on the work of Maria Sturken and Lisa Cartwright, this article takes the position that while images as visual objects do carry meaning in and of themselves, the practices surrounding image circulation and consumption also produce particular complementary or contradictory meanings in the moment of interaction.⁵⁴ This position goes beyond analyses that interrogate how images ‘speak’ and become political objects, which locate interpretation and agency through the combination of text and image, to consider the role of communication technology in mediating images and what they are taken to articulate, and by whom.⁵⁵ As such, there is a politics that exists within the relationship between people and things, which both mediates and is mediated by the interactive performance of technology and the body: social media images are both produced and consumed in movement, across body and touch.⁵⁶

⁵¹ Callahan, *Sensible Politics*, p.35; E. Hutchison, ‘Affective communities as security communities’, *Critical Studies on Security* 1:1(2013), pp. 127-129.

⁵² L. Amore, ‘Vigilant visualities: The watchful politics of the war on terror’, *Security Dialogue* 38:2(2008), p. 223; see also K. Krause, ‘Disentangling the protection suit: Images, artefacts and the making of the health-security nexus’, *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* 49:3 (2021), pp. 472-497; Callahan, *Sensible Politics*.

⁵³ D. Etherington, ‘X will now preserve JPEG quality for photo uploads on the web’, *TechCrunch*, 11 December 2019.

⁵⁴ M. Sturken and L. Cartwright, *Practices of Looking: An Introduction to Visual Culture* (Oxford: Oxford University Press), 2001.

⁵⁵ R. Saugmann Andersen, ‘Video, algorithms and security: How digital video platforms produce post-sovereign security articulations’, *Security Dialogue* 48:4 (2017), pp. 354-372, p. 365; G. Schlag and A. Heck, ‘Securitizing images: The female body and the war in Afghanistan’, *European Journal of International Relations* 19:4 (2013), pp. 891-913; L. Hansen, ‘Theorizing the image for security studies: Visual securitization and the Muhammad cartoon crisis’, *European Journal of International Relations* 17:1 (2011), pp. 51-74; L. Stone, ‘Are you breathing? Do you have Email Apnea?’, 24 November 2014, available at: <https://lindastone.net/2014/11/24/are-you-breathing-do-you-have-email-apnea/>, accessed on 8 April 2024.

⁵⁶ H.R. Markussen, ‘Conceptualising the smartphone as a security device: Appropriations of embodied connectivity at the Black Lives Matter protests’, *Critical Studies on Security* 10:2 (2022), pp. 70-84, p. 71; R. Saugmann, ‘The security captor, captured: Digital cameras, visual politics and material semiotics’, *Critical Studies on Security* 8:2 (2020), pp. 130-144; A. Amicelle, C. Aradau and J. Jeandesboz, ‘Questioning security devices: Performativity, resistance, politics’, *Security Dialogue* 46:4 (2015), pp. 293-306; S. Pink, ‘Sensory digital photography: re-thinking “moving” and the image’, *Visual Studies* 26:1 (2011), pp. 4-13, p. 6; Rose, *Visual methodologies*, pp. 34-38.

Below I elaborate on the tripartite theoretical framework of See-Touch-Feel to develop a deeper appreciation of this multisensory interaction by taking into account how users *see* Twitter images – via the algorithms that contribute to the visibility and circulation of images; how users *touch* the images – via the relationship between the platform interface and material technology such as smartphone or tablet screens that shape its technological affordances; and how users can *feel*, or feel about, these images – via the screen-body entanglement. I draw on political philosophy interrogations into the commonsense ‘mind-body, reason-senses model’ to draw out the relationality between digital technology and the sensing body of the user as a political process, which foregrounds the role of bodily movement and touch in the intersection of images, affect and bodies.⁵⁷ I deploy this three-part framework – how we *see* Twitter images, the ways in which we *touch* Twitter images, and what this does to how we *feel* about them – to allow for a speculative interpretation of how human and non-human elements play into Twitter image circulation, consumption, and response.

See

Here I explore the role of algorithms in conditioning how social media images are seen, and the ways in which touch is implicated in the development and emergence of algorithmic processes that heighten circulation of digital images. As each social media platform has its own, individual algorithm, I focus on Twitter to trace the relationality of circulation as conditioned through both algorithm and human touch. Twitter allows users to ‘tweet’, or post, short statements about ‘what’s happening’. Initially developed as an intimate space for friends to keep in touch via its structure of instant messages and activity updates, the platform was quickly adopted as the preferred medium through which diplomats and political leaders communicate with their counterparts and wider domestic and foreign publics.⁵⁸ With 350 million users globally, Twitter is less popular than other social media platforms such as Facebook (2.9 billion) or Instagram (2.3 billion), but it has nevertheless remained the preferred social media platform for professional use among diplomats and political leaders worldwide (Møller et al 2024; Harris and Lin-Greenberg 2024). The structure of Twitter itself is what makes the social media platform so attractive for political leaders and

⁵⁷ E. Manning, *Politics of touch: Sense, movement, sovereignty* (University of Minnesota Press, 2007), p. xii; Åhäll, ‘Affect as methodology’; see also S. Malaviya, ‘Digitising the virtual: Movement and relations in drone warfare’, *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* 49:1 (2020), pp. 80-104, Leander, ‘Locating (new) materialist characters’, p. 162; D. Haraway, ‘A manifesto for cyborgs: science, technology, and socialist feminism in the 1980s’, in D.T. Meyers (ed.) *Feminist Social Thought: A Reader* (New York: Routledge, 1997 [1985]), pp. 502–31; R. Sooryamoorthy, ‘Inside the mobile world and outside the Internet’, *New Media and Society* 16(2014), pp. 165-170.

⁵⁸ J. Burgess J and N.K. Baym, *Twitter: A biography* (New York: NYU Press, 2020), p. 3.

diplomats. Users can ‘tweet’ or communicate directly with one another, but anyone can view these messages if the user has their Twitter @name handle (username) open and publicly available.⁵⁹ Such exchanges go beyond personal interaction, as tweets are broadcast to a much wider audience. Twitter is therefore ‘very international’, with ‘large and active populations of users outside the English-speaking’, including in countries such as China and Iran where the service is officially blocked.⁶⁰ Furthermore, the vast majority of Twitter users (over 80%) access the platform via their smartphone, either through the Twitter application or via an open webpage, so the user has a continuous and almost always-on connection to the platform.

An algorithm influences the circulation and frequency of posts and external media links platform users are exposed to.⁶¹ Algorithms – what Louise Amoore and Rita Raley define as ‘both technical process and synecdoche for ever more complex and opaque socio-technical assemblages’ – work below the surface of the social media interface.⁶² Algorithms can structure content feeds based on not only the ‘top’ or most relevant posts, tweets or stories, but also in terms of content similar to what the user had previously engaged with and would therefore be likely to engage with in the future.⁶³ For example, in reference to concerns regarding ‘echo chambers’ and content feed saturation of only narrow viewpoints, Brooke Auxier and Jessica Vitak suggest that ‘if a user regularly follows, “likes”, and engages with conservative, right-leaning news content, the algorithm will likely surface more conservative, right-leaning content’.⁶⁴ As such, content is personalized to the user based on prediction and maximizing user behaviours including clicks, views, likes and comments.⁶⁵

⁵⁹ Burgess and Bruns, ‘(Not) the Twitter election?’.

⁶⁰ Burgess and Baym, *Twitter*, p. 3.

⁶¹ J. Bandy and N. Diakopoulos, ‘Curating Quality? How Twitter’s Timeline Algorithm Treats Different Types of News’, *Social Media + Society* 7:3 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051211041648>

⁶² L. Amoore R. Raley, ‘Securing with algorithms: Knowledge, decision, sovereignty’, *Security Dialogue* 48:1 (2017): pp. 3-10, p 3.

⁶³ B.E. Auxier and J. Vitak, ‘Factors motivating customization and echo chamber creation within digital news environments’, *Social media+ society* 5:2 (2019); B. Latour, *Reassembling the social: An introduction to actor-network-theory* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005); C. Aradau and Tobias Blanke, ‘Governing others: Anomaly and the algorithmic subject of security’, *European Journal of International Security* 3(2017), pp. 1-21; A. Mitchell, ‘Only human? A wordly approach to security’, *Security Dialogue* 45(2014), pp. 5-21.

⁶⁴ Auxier and Vitak, ‘Factors motivating customization and echo chamber creation?’.

⁶⁵ S. Milli, M. Carroll, Y. Wang, S. Pandey, S. Zhao and A.D. Dragan, ‘Engagement, User Satisfaction, and the Amplification of Divisive Content on Social Media’, available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2305.16941.pdf>, accessed on 13 November 2023.

Up until 2016, the Twitter platform displayed tweets on a user's homepage feed according to reverse chronological order.⁶⁶ After this time, user interaction with the platform has become conditioned through algorithmic curation as the default option.⁶⁷ Twitter's 'For You' timeline forces a non-chronological selection of tweets to the top of users' feeds via 'posts from accounts and Topics you follow as well as recommended posts'.⁶⁸ This has enabled a significant boost in user engagement with tweets, and more specifically an increase in engagement with shorter tweets and those with more sensationalist content, as defined by emotionally loaded words and exclamation marks.⁶⁹ Social features of Twitter are time sensitive, such as the @mention or @reply features that function to provide a 'form of "addressivity" that references others, either as the intended recipient, as a third person being talked about, or a response to someone else's tweet'.⁷⁰ As a result, tweets mentioning the same Twitter user within the same short time period are more likely to refer to the same topic, which contributes to the rise in position of key events, debates, or select users within the Twitter algorithm.⁷¹ Furthermore, tweets from elite users garner far more attention, which is a 'peculiar reinforcement of Twitter's powerful function as a public relations tool'.⁷² The need for in-the-moment response and the tacility of user behaviour via Twitter platform affordances allows Twitter users to participate in the circulation of digital images. Interpersonal engagement with tweeted images through likes, @reply or @mention icons both creates a sense of intimacy and draws attention to tweeted images as part of this public-private conversation. Public discussions become visible to a global audience without the need for prior personal connections such as befriending or following other users.⁷³

Yet an important facet of the development of the Twitter algorithm is the curation of content via individual user engagement with tweets on the platform: the algorithm emerges from the physical practice of scrolling on a screen, touching a tweet to 'like' or 'quote' it, or to reply

⁶⁶ E. Dujancourt and M. Garz, 'The effects of algorithmic content selection on user engagement with news on Twitter', *The Information Society*, 39:5 (2023), pp. 263-281.

⁶⁷ Dujancourt and Garz, 'The effects of algorithmic content selection'.

⁶⁸ 'For You Home Timeline Recommendations', Twitter, <https://help.twitter.com/en/resources/recommender-systems/for-you-home-timeline-recommendations>, accessed 10 November 2023.

⁶⁹ Dujancourt and Garz, 'The effects of algorithmic content selection', p. 277.

⁷⁰ S. Tanupabrungrsun and J. Hemsley, 'Studying celebrity practices on TWitter using a framework for measuring media richness', *Social Media + Society* 4:1(2018), p. 2.

⁷¹ R. Nugroho, C. Paris, S. Nepal, J. Yang and W. Zhao, 'A survey of recent methods on deriving topics from Twitter: algorithm to evaluation', *Knowledge and information systems* 62:7 (2020): pp. 2485-2519.

⁷² Van Dijck and Poell, 'Understanding social media logic', p.7.

⁷³ S. Meraz and Z. Papacharissi. 'Networked gatekeeping and networked framing on# Egypt', *The international journal of press/politics* 18:2(2013), pp. 138-166; C. Duncombe, 'Social media and the visibility of horrific violence', *International Affairs* 96:3 (2020), pp. 609-629.

directly to the user who posted it. Rather than simply passive viewers, users will use their fingers and thumbs to physically manifest greater spread and attention to these digital images by pressing the retweet or like buttons that frame the outside of the image. Twitter users physically engage with photographs in a way that is not possible with conventional news media images printed in newspapers or shown on television. Twitter users have, therefore, a 'greater latitude to creatively repurpose digital content rather than passively absorb it'.⁷⁴ What you touch – selecting tweets or images as you scroll through the Twitter homepage – contributes to conditioning the algorithm that makes tweets and their accompanying images visible to you when you log on to the platform. The 'trending' algorithm on Twitter can make some topics immediately visible in preference to others, which consequently pushes some images forward in circulation and underplays others. This feature effectively privileges instantaneous and immediate engagement, which also may amplify 'emotionally charged, out-group hostile content and contribute to affective polarization'.⁷⁵ As such, the more a user physically interacts with the platform via clicks, likes, views or comments, the more emotionally-charged content is being amplified by the algorithm, leading to an increasing likelihood that the user will in turn click on, like, view or comment on tweets signifying anger or outrage, which again become further amplified via user behaviour as technologically-mediated content curation.

This amplification is further intensified through the rhythm associated with liking or 'hearting' tweets, which encourage individuals as platform users to 'click' the heart or retweet icon as a method for scripting their identities as belonging to the platform community and their extended online networks.⁷⁶ The rhythmic action of pushing the thumb or forefinger against the smartphone screen, moving the digit along the smooth surface, and clicking the heart, retweet or quote tweet icons assists in the co-constitution of digital Twitter communities. These rhythmic actions can be conceptualised as 'sticky', cohering the individual to a collective because 'prompts from interfaces, likes and other reactions, and cultural conventions encourage people to continually log in, respond, and be tied to interfaces because of their adhesive and tempting

⁷⁴ Ross, 'Emotion and Experience in International Relations', p. 171; L. Manovich, 'The practice of everyday (media) life: From mass consumption to mass cultural production?', *Critical Inquiry* 35:2(2009), pp. 319-331.

⁷⁵ Milli et al, 'Engagement, User Satisfaction, and the Amplification of Divisive Content on Social Media', p. 1, 6; T. Highfield and T. Leaver, 'Instagrammatics and digital methods: Studying visual social media, from selfies and GIFs to memes and emoji', *Communication research and practice* 2:1(2016), p. 50; Van Dijck and Poell, 'Understanding social media logic', p.5.

⁷⁶ White, *Touch Screen Theory*, p. 27; T. Solomon, 'Up in the air: Ritualized atmospheres and the global Black Lives Matter movement', *European Journal of International Relations* 29(2023), p. 578.

features'.⁷⁷ Thus the relationality between human and algorithm act in concert to govern the (in)visibility of digital images tweeted on Twitter, and how they are circulated.⁷⁸

Touch

Here I examine the relationship between the interface – the ‘zone of connection, experience, communication, and performance between humans and a digital system’⁷⁹ – and material technology, to demonstrate how touch is implicated in conditioning how social media images are seen via the interaction and operationalization of the relationship between visual artefacts and digital platforms. The virtual interface of social media platforms, with their specific functions and processes, and the material hardware of the smartphone, contribute to design properties that shape user interaction through touch.

Twitter was ‘born mobile’ in its platform design, and smartphones were built to host applications for digital social media platforms like Twitter.⁸⁰ The material hardware used to access Twitter images, particularly the smartphone, becomes central to the circulation and consumption of digital images on Twitter. Mobile usage worldwide has increased so much that the smartphone has become ubiquitous.⁸¹ Smartphones have enabled the affordance of the platform to record in-the-moment actions and updates, tying the hand-held device to the quotidian rhythms of our day.⁸² Even more so, the very construction of the device – slim, designed to fit in the hand and pocket – reinforces its desired use as a flexible tool.⁸³ We carry our smartphones with us during our day, such that the ‘relative ease of taking out a mobile device, both within the rhythm of a domestic

⁷⁷ White, *Touch Screen Theory*, p. 10; A. Cho, ‘Default publicness: Queer youth of color, social media, and being outed by the machine’, *New Media & Society* 20(2018), pp. 3183-3200.

⁷⁸ Leander, ‘Locating (new) materialist characters’, p. 162.

⁷⁹ P. Maia ‘The Case for Interfaces in International Relations’, *Global Studies Quarterly* (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1093/isagsq/ksad054>

⁸⁰ Twitter, ‘New Compete study: Primary mobile users on Twitter’, available at https://blog.twitter.com/en_us/a/2013/new-compete-study-primary-mobile-users-on-twitter#:~:text=Today%2C%20mobile%20is%20often%20the,at%20least%20once%20every%20month, accessed on 13 November 2023.

⁸¹ D. Murthy, S. Bowman, A.J. Gross and M. McGarry, ‘Do we tweet differently from our mobile devices? A study of language differences on mobile and web-based Twitter platforms’, *Journal of Communication* 65:5(2015), p. 816.

⁸² Murthy, Bowman, Gross and McGarry, ‘Do we tweet differently from our mobile devices?’, p. 817; B. Hutchins, ‘The acceleration of media sport culture: Twitter, telepresence and online messaging’, *Information, Communication & Society* 14:2(2011), p. 240.

⁸³ For an analysis of the gendered, racialized and ableist nature of the design properties of the smartphone, digital platforms, and their genres of use, see White, *Touch Screen Theory*; Cho, ‘Default publicness’; G. Goggin, ‘Disability and haptic mobile media’, *New Media & Society* 19(2017), pp. 1563-1580.

routine, or while navigating public space, visual sharing can approach synchronous time'.⁸⁴ For instance, smartphones can be held in one hand while the user is completing other tasks or activities (eating, or holding something, being on the move, for example).⁸⁵ The small data size of tweets, even with images included, means smartphones can easily send and receive tweets.⁸⁶ As a result, smartphones have 'led to an "untether[ing] from static computer terminals" and have facilitated interactions that are "interwoven increasingly with daily experience"'.⁸⁷

One may argue that smartphone screens act as a physical barrier between the user and the image, giving 'the appearance of a detached, smart, data-driven basis for decision',⁸⁸ lacking the tactility of friction or roughness as a finger turns a page in a newspaper or book. Yet in producing this artificial distance, the screen effectively draws the viewer in, enticing them to move toward the displayed images and transporting the viewer beyond themselves into the online space within which the images circulate and are made discursively meaningful, reinforcing the inextricable link between virtual and material spaces.⁸⁹ How this link between the online screenic and offline worlds occur is through touch, specifically through the manipulation of the smartphone screen by an individual's fingers. The role of touch – how users handle and physically engage with their smartphones and smartphone screen – is intrinsic to their affective experience of the platform interface and its functionality.⁹⁰ In presenting the first iteration of the iPhone, on which modern smartphones are based, Steve Jobs introduced the concept of 'multi-touch' as the foundational technological advancement of communications technology: 'We're going to use the best pointing device in the world...[one] we're all born with – born with ten of them. We're going to use our fingers. We're going to touch this with our fingers'. Specifically created, therefore, for use with the fingers, the multi-touch sensing screen depends on the electrical conductivity provided by bare skin.⁹¹ Patterns vibro-tactile sensations communicated through the skin when someone swipes across the screen can induce the illusion that icons displayed on/behind the screen have a physical

⁸⁴ Zappavigna, 'Social media photography', p. 272.

⁸⁵ Zappavigna, 'Social media photography', p. 283.

⁸⁶ Murthy, Bowman, Gross and McGarry, 'Do we tweet differently from our mobile devices?', p. 817.

⁸⁷ Page [2012: 7] cited in Murthy, Bowman, Gross and McGarry, 'Do we tweet differently from our mobile devices?', p. 818; S. Vivienne and J. Burgess, 'The remediation of the personal photograph and the politics of self-representation in digital storytelling', *Journal of Material Culture* 18:3(2013), p. 283.

⁸⁸ Amore, 'Vigilant visualities', p. 222.

⁸⁹ H.R. Cooley, 'It's all about the fit: The hand, the mobile screenic device and tactile vision', *Journal of Visual Culture* 3:2(2004), p. 143; Amore, 'Vigilant visualities', p. 223; C. Weber, 'Popular visual language as global communication: the remediation of United Airlines Flight 93', *Review of International Studies* 34(2008), p. 138; Jackson and Valentine, 'Emotion and politics in a mediated public sphere', p. 194.

⁹⁰ Richardson and Hjorth, 'Mobile media, domestic play and haptic ethnography', p. 1658.

⁹¹ Richardson and Hjorth, 'Mobile media, domestic play and haptic ethnography', p. 1661.

weight or mass, such that clicking on the Twitter application or logging in to Twitter via webpage on a smartphone has a transitional quality: moving, physically, from one space to another through this naïve physics rendering the touchscreen an ‘object of tactile and kinaesthetic familiarity’ akin to ‘haptic intimacy’.⁹² This, in turn, means the user can experience an ‘always-on channel of communication’ through the skin through these sensations shaped by the screen, a ‘notification culture’ that has quietly worked its way into everyday life.⁹³

Seeing Twitter images therefore involves both material hardware and user interaction via touch.⁹⁴ Every act of reaching towards the screen, of touching the smartphone with your fingers, ‘enables the creation of worlds’ that through constant repetition of this relationality shape the subjectivity of the individual: ‘I reach out to touch you in order to invent a relation that will, in turn, invent me’.⁹⁵ It is less about what viewers see, but rather how it is they see the images circulating over Twitter.⁹⁶ There is a sensation of pleasure, wherein the experience of holding the smartphone in one hand and scrolling (using the thumb of the same hand or another finger from the opposite hand) allows the material hardware to fold intimately into the physical site of the body. A bonding occurs between image, user and smartphone, which produces a “mystical feel” that arises out of a “combination of a good mechanical marriage and something in the nervous system”.⁹⁷ This ‘innervating exchange’ encourages an engagement with or connection to an image, overcoming the often-times sense of detachment that could arise from viewing an image on a screen.⁹⁸ In fact, the concept of ‘nomophobia’ has developed to signify the fear people have of losing control over their lives if detached from their smartphone and digital connectivity.⁹⁹ Twitter images have, therefore, a different kind of potential to evoke or represent emotions, precisely because these images become an extension of the hand, rendering any barrier between online and offline worlds obsolete through this force of movement. In fact, the embodiment of emotion derived from seeing Twitter images is enhanced by the individualization derived from

⁹² Richardson and Hjorth, ‘Mobile media, domestic play and haptic ethnography’, p. 1661.

⁹³ M. Paterson, ‘On haptic media and the possibility of a more inclusive interactivity’, *New Media & Society* 19(2017), p. 1549; M. White, *Touch screen theory: Digital devices and feelings* (MIT Press, 2022), p. 2; D. Parisi, M. Paterson and J.E. Archer, ‘Haptic media studies’, *New Media and Society* 19(2017), pp. 1514-1515; Goggin, ‘Disability and haptic mobile media’, p. 1572.

⁹⁴ Cooley, ‘It’s all about the fit’, p. 135.

⁹⁵ Manning, *Politics of touch*, p. xv.

⁹⁶ Cooley, ‘It’s all about the fit’, p. 135; J. Berger, *Ways of seeing* (Penguin UK, 2008).

⁹⁷ Wilson [1999] cited in Cooley, ‘It’s all about the fit’, p. 139.

⁹⁸ Cooley, ‘It’s all about the fit’, p. 141.

⁹⁹ R. Wei, ‘Evolving mobile media: Changing technology and transforming behaviour’, *Mobile Media and Communication* 11(2023), p. 27.

using a smartphone: Dhiraj Murthy et al have found that tweets sent over mobile devices tend to use more egocentric language.¹⁰⁰ Accessing Twitter via a smartphone is also necessarily more intimate because ‘most users do not share their cellphone’¹⁰¹: it is kept close to the body, in their hand, a jacket or pants pocket, a bag they are holding, on a table or desk they are using, next to their bed. Any notification alerts vibrate through the body, because of this close, intimate relationship of the smartphone to an individual user.¹⁰² Thus the experience of seeing an image within the technosocial space of Twitter is framed by the affordances of the platform that emphasise ego-centric, individualized experience first and foremost, which at the very least has reconfigured the rules of social interactions and consequently ‘the social context of intimacy’.¹⁰³ This reconfiguration of the social is nonetheless buttressed by the transformation of affective networks through the creation of an ‘intimate visual co-presence’.¹⁰⁴ It is not simply the affordances of the platform that allows this; rather it is the images themselves, as a separate feature of Twitter, that coalesce with the structure of the platform to generate these networked emotional logics.

Feel

Here I explore the role of the body in facilitating how social media images are seen via the interaction between visual artefact, touch, and emotional resonance. The multisensory nature of digital platforms allows users to feel images, precisely because of the ‘body’s leakiness and continuity with its surrounds’.¹⁰⁵ I show how this phenomenon is communicated from one person to another, from the individual to the group.¹⁰⁶

Touching a social media image can heighten emotional resonance that contributes to an embodied interaction, which is not just cognitive but also physical. As Manni Crone argues, the ‘senses of seeing, hearing and touching are situated in the body and closely linked to the body’s

¹⁰⁰ Murthy, Bowman, Gross and McGarry, ‘Do we tweet differently from our mobile devices?’, p. 834.

¹⁰¹ Murthy, Bowman, Gross and McGarry, ‘Do we tweet differently from our mobile devices?’, p. 818; M. Chae and J. Kim, ‘What’s so different about the mobile Internet?’, *Communications of the ACM* 46:12(2003), pp. 240-247.

¹⁰² Goggin, ‘Disability and haptic mobile media’, p. 1573.

¹⁰³ Ross, ‘Emotion and Experience in International Relations’, p. 171; Ibrahim, ‘The unsacred and the spectacularized’, p. 2; Van Dijck and Poell, ‘Understanding social media logic’, p. 3.

¹⁰⁴ M. Ito and D. Okabe, ‘Intimate visual co-presence’, *2005 Ubiquitous Computing Conference*; Zappavigna, ‘Social media photography’, p. 272.

¹⁰⁵ T. Aistrop, ‘Popular culture, the body and world politics’, *European Journal of International Relations* 2:1(2020), p. 169; D. Lisle, ‘A speculative lexicon of entanglement’, *Millennium* 49:3 (2021), pp. 435-461.

¹⁰⁶ C. Jewitt, K. Leder Mackley and S. Price, ‘Digital touch for remote personal communication: An emergent sociotechnical imaginary’, *New Media & Society* 23:1 (2021): pp. 99-120.

experience of pain and pleasure'.¹⁰⁷ Our body responds to emotion through physiological arousal, such as the bodily response to something we see as frightening; an elevated heart rate, hair standing on end, dry mouth, tense muscles: 'seeing is a physiological experience of a lived body'.¹⁰⁸ These feelings – for example, horror can produce nausea, revulsion, disgust, excitement, pleasure – influence how we see and understand an image through the 'twisted braid of affect and thought'.¹⁰⁹ Touching a digital image with fingers or thumbs is felt as emotionally resonant via this body in movement: reaching the hand towards the smartphone, grasping it, manipulating the interface with finger and thumb to access the platform and the tweets that are produced within it meshes the hand with device such that 'hands also touch screens and individuals experience screens as touching'.¹¹⁰ The dualism of the body – as touching and being touched – is relational and intersubjective, an overlap between physical presence and perceptual meaning.¹¹¹

This imbrication of the body in relations with the digital becomes an experience that binds people together and produces networks of feeling.¹¹² As Sara Ahmed argues, a physical co-presence is not necessary for individuals to stick together as a group: the 'surfaces of collective bodies' manifest through the touchscreen as a substitute for the skin, which meshes into the hand and intensifies a connection between the smartphone, corporeality and feelings.¹¹³ This is particularly helpful in understanding how digital intimacy of ambient networks is constructed, and the ways in which we might be more attuned to the role of touch in the embodied and affective engagement with digital media.¹¹⁴

A powerful example of the body as already mediated in meaning-making processes is the act of doomsurfing, or doomscrolling. Doomscrolling refers to users scrolling and clicking through their social media timelines reading bad news. Kevin Roose has helpfully described this practice as 'falling into deep, morbid rabbit holes filled with coronavirus content, agitating myself to the point

¹⁰⁷ Crone, 'It's a man's world', p. 579.

¹⁰⁸ Crone, 'It's a man's world', p. 580; C. Walsh, *Cowardice: a brief history* (Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 2014), p. 83; E. Hutchison and R. Bleiker, 'Theorizing emotions in world politics', *International Theory* 6(2014), p. 501.

¹⁰⁹ J. Kristeva, *Powers of horror* (University Presses of California, Columbia and Princeton, 1982), p. 1.

¹¹⁰ White, *Touch Screen Theory*, p. 11; Cooley, 'It's all about the fit', p. 141.

¹¹¹ Merleau-Ponty, *The visible and the invisible*, pp. 136-138.

¹¹² Leander, 'Locating (new) materialist characters', p. 160; S. Ahmed, 'Collective Feelings: Or, the Impressions Left by Others', *Theory, Culture & Society* 21(2004), pp. 25-42.

¹¹³ Ahmed, 'Collective feelings'; White, *Touch Screen Theory*, p. 10, 27; Cooley, 'It's all about the fit', p. 141.

¹¹⁴ M. Zappavigna, 'Digital intimacy and ambient embodied copresence in YouTube videos: Constructing visual-aural perspective in ASMR role play videos', *Visual Communication* (2020), p.1; I. Richardson and L. Hjorth, 'Mobile media, domestic play and haptic ethnography', *New media and society* 19(2017), p. 1654; S. Pink, 'Approaching media through the senses: Between experience and representation', *Media International Australia* 154 (2015), pp. 5-14.

of physical discomfort, erasing any hope of a good night's sleep'.¹¹⁵ Although in the COVID-19 pandemic environment doomscrolling became a normalised behaviour, the practice nonetheless creates or feeds anxiety by trapping users in a 'vicious cycle of negativity': "Our minds are wired to look out for threats", she says. "The more time we spend scrolling, the more we find those dangers, the more we get sucked into them, the more anxious we get... Now you look around yourself, and everything feels gloomy, everything makes you anxious. So you go back to look for more information".¹¹⁶ The physicality of doomscrolling practice is such that it manifests anxiety in its embodiment: hunched in bed late at night or in the early morning hours, eyes fixated on the screen with the smartphone close to our face in the dark, neck cricked, thumbs or forefingers working overtime. It upends our circadian rhythm, pushing our bodies further away from rest and recovery from daily activity to its draining physical limit.

Yet this contortion of the body is not unique to doomscrolling: the repetitive act of engaging with social media platforms such as Twitter on a smartphone has a high correlation with neck and upper back pain, decreased, disrupted, or delayed sleep, joint inflammation in the hands, particularly the thumb or index finger joints, eye strain and tension headaches. Users can also hold or change their breath patterns in what Linda Stone has called 'screen apnea', putting increasing pressure on the sympathetic nervous system that regulates stress.¹¹⁷ Furthermore, there is increasing demand on the sympathetic nervous system because the narrow visual field of the smartphone screen requires a much more intense focus to exclude everything outside of it, to fully focus.¹¹⁸ The embodied experience of social media becomes one of a curled neck and spine, tensed shoulders and abdomen, lungs expanded and held, arm and hand extended and eyes centimetres from the screen.

We are not exposed to repetitive negative news or images of horrific violence just through our doomscrolling practices: violent imagery of all kinds is widely and freely available across public facing social media platforms, such that 'blood and human carnage' is passively absorbed as we scroll through our social media platform timeline.¹¹⁹ The provocation of emotions becomes

¹¹⁵ K. Roose, 'The week in tech: How to stop Coronavirus "doomscrolling"', *The New York Times*, 20 March 2020, available at { <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/03/20/technology/coronavirus-doomsurfing.html> }, accessed 15 June 2023.

¹¹⁶ Aldao cited in L. Garcia-Navarro, 'Your 'Doomscrolling' Breeds Anxiety. Here's How To Stop The Cycle', *NPR*, 19 July 2020, available at { <https://www.npr.org/2020/07/19/892728595/your-doomscrolling-breeds-anxiety-here-s-how-to-stop-the-cycle> }, accessed 15 June 2023.

¹¹⁷ Stone, 'Are you breathing?'

¹¹⁸ A.H. Gupta, 'Checking email? You're probably not breathing', *The New York Times*, 21 August 2023, available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/08/21/well/live/screen-apnea-breathing.html>, accessed on 11 April 2024.

¹¹⁹ S. Redmond, N.M. Jones, E.A. Holman and R.C. Silver, 'Who watches an ISIS beheading—And why', *American Psychologist* 74:5(2019), p. 555.

particularly acute when a user is exposed to violent or traumatic images. Real-time public access to traumatic events has been facilitated through the technological evolution at the intersection between smartphone technology and social media.¹²⁰ The combination of graphic images as more likely to capture a viewer's attention and the algorithmic drive of Twitter facilitating more emotionally charged tweets means the circulation of violent or traumatic images becomes increasingly amplified.¹²¹ Images in a user's Twitter feed (what they see on their homepage) are compressed thumbnails that are algorithmically cropped to enable the image to fit within a tweet; to see the full, uncompressed image, the user needs to select the tweet and click through to open it up and see the image and any quoted text in full.¹²² Thus users need to touch these violent images in order to see them fully, which contributes to the increased circulation of the image and the likelihood the user will see the image more than once due to this algorithmic amplification. The ease with which these images are revealed to us can further exacerbate pre-existing fears of violence and atrocity, producing a physical response to the horror, anxiety or anger elicited by extremist violence. Yet these violent images are complex and contentious in their own ways, producing complex feelings in the viewer. The ultraviolence and barbarism of Islamic State social media posts offers a powerful example of this dynamic. While political leaders characterised IS beheading videos as 'beyond anything we have ever seen', showing the 'very worst of humanity', some audiences were able to 'dream, feel pleasure or imagine themselves inhabiting those images'.¹²³ Even more so, some spectators felt compelled to join the group after viewing this horrific imagery.

The entanglements of the material-body, human-non-human connection therefore allows the user to be immersed in the experience of seeing, shifting an experience from 'something that is acquired in the first person [that] you have to be there to have the experience', to one that is 'acquired in the virtual first-person'.¹²⁴ To understand how the body is in contact with other bodies we need to consider the embodied experience of consuming social media.

Imagining Touch in Practice

¹²⁰ E.A. Holman, D.R. Garfin and R.C. Silver, 'Media exposure to collective trauma, mental health, and functioning: Does it matter what you see?', *Clinical Psychological Science* 8:1 (2019), pp. 111-124.

¹²¹ K. Riddle, 'A theory of vivid media violence', *Communication Theory* 24 (2014), pp. 291-310; Duncombe, 'Social media and the visibility of horrific violence'.

¹²² D. Etherington, 'Twitter will now preserve JPEG quality for photo uploads on the web', *TechCrunch*, 11 December 2019.

¹²³ Crone, 'It's a man's world', p. 574.

¹²⁴ Weber, 'Popular visual language as global communication', p. 140; A. Kanai, 'Jennifer Lawrence, remixed: approaching celebrity through DIY digital culture', *Celebrity studies* 6:3(2015), p. 323.

I now extend my theorisation of the role of touch in experiencing social media images by illustrating how diplomatic representatives, policymakers and political staffers may have interacted with the Wuheqilin image, so called because the image itself was a digital artwork constructed by Wuheqilin, a graphic artist known for creating nationalist propaganda-infused work (Image 1., pictured below). In building an over-the-shoulder narrative of the circulation and consumption of the Wuheqilin image, I show – via a theoretically grounded skilful speculation – why and how touch matters when we analyse social media images and their perceived effects. I begin by describing the image and how it circulated, then use the see-touch-feel framework to speculate, theoretically, about how it resonated with the key actors who saw the tweet.

The formal composition of the image is the first layer of understanding how the tweet became the subject of a significant diplomatic spat. As a composition, the image uses a photoshopped photograph or constructed image of a grinning Australian soldier holding a knife to the throat of a child. The blue veil of the Australian flag covers the child's face, obscuring it, but the cloth is transparent enough to see features such as eyes and an open mouth with teeth. The soldier is pulling back the head of the child; the child's wide eyes and open mouth makes it seem as though it is screaming. The knife blade is covered in dark red colour suggestive of blood; the placement of the knife and the split across the blue fabric suggests the soldier has already slit the throat of the child or other children not visualised in the image. The child is standing with bare feet, holding a lamb. The soldier is crouching over the child, standing on Australian flag, which covers the Afghanistan flag that is segmented into puzzle pieces. The Australian flag is raised in certain places in a semi-circle around the soldier-child image, with body-like shapes visible underneath.

Image 1. Tweet by Zhou Lijian with the composite artwork by WuheQilin, 30 November 2020.

The polysemic nature of the image itself means it can be visually read in many ways: the composition of the image and its inter-iconicity, including image denotation, interpretations and the interplay of colour, text and image type, allows for a multitude of visual representations to take hold.¹²⁵ For instance, the interplay of three generic icons – the lamb, the child, and the soldier – overlay visual metaphors that are highly religious, militarised, or gendered, resonating with the viewer in different ways depending on their positionality. The visual intertext of the child as a sacrifice overlaps with Christian metaphors representing Jesus Christ as the lamb of God, who suffered and died for the sins of humanity. A strong visual intertext is evident with the 1662 Bartolomé Esteban Murillo painting ‘The Infant St John with the Lamb’, which shows St John the Baptist as a barefoot child embracing a lamb that is taken as a symbol of Christ as the Good Shepherd.¹²⁶ The lamb in the Murillo painting and in the Wuheqilin work are of similar size and placement, depicted from the side being held closely by the child.

¹²⁵ L. Hansen, ‘How images make world politics: International icons and the case of Abu Ghraib’, *Review of International Studies* 41:2(2015), pp 263-288; Rune Saugmann Andersen, J.A. Vuori & Xavier Guillaume, ‘Chromatology of security: Introducing colours to visual security studies’, *Security Dialogue* 46:5(2015), pp. 440–457.

¹²⁶ The National Gallery { <https://www.nationalgallery.org.uk/paintings/bartolome-esteban-murillo-the-infant-saint-john-with-the-lamb> }.

Meanwhile the anchoring text shapes the meaning of what the composite image conveys through a discursive frame of war crimes allegations against Australian troops. The overlaid image text – ‘don’t be afraid, we are coming to bring you peace!’ – and the tweet caption by Zhou Lijian, ‘Shocked by murder of Afghan prisoners & civilians by Australian soldiers. We strongly condemn such acts, & call for holding them accountable’ – clearly link the image to the ‘Brereton report’, the result of an inquiry into serious allegations of unlawful killings of civilians and their cover-up by elite Australian soldiers, which, if taken to trial, would constitute war crimes.¹²⁷ This also mirrors the intention of the artist Wuheqilin, who wanted to create a ‘facts-based image’ drawing attention to the unlawful killings by Australian soldiers.¹²⁸ Rendering the child as another war crime victim visually represents claims raised in the Brereton report that members of the Special Air Service Regiment (SAS) cut the throats of two 14-year-old Afghan boys, which were never substantiated. Australia represents itself as a ‘good international citizen’ middle power, an identity formed through militarized myths of ‘mateship’ and mutual sacrifice in war that tie together its relationships with allies in the region and beyond.¹²⁹ The tweet text and caption anchors the image to a fundamental challenge to these identity narratives, visually representing the violent behaviour of Australian armed forces as authentic and signalling contempt for the hypocrisy of the Australian government in how it strategically represents Australia internationally.

By midday on 30 November 2020, I speculate that Australian policymakers, and diplomats, including Prime Minister Scott Morrison, would most likely have already checked their social media accounts at least once already. In the singular, a person in this group would have conceivably woken up, turned off their alarm (which most probably was on their smartphone), reached out to grab their smartphone and swiped or pressed their thumb against the screen surface to unlock their device. After clicking on the messages app to check any texts that came in overnight, they might then check their email app or their Twitter app – these icons would have small red number badges signifying the counts of how many email or tweet notifications this person has. Either lying in bed or pushing themselves into a seated position on their mattress, with a bent neck and hunched shoulders, breathing shallow or held, they would scroll through their Twitter timeline to see the latest news and trending topics, use their thumb or forefinger to click on their messages and expand any tweets to see their content in full, including any comments by other users. They

¹²⁷ C. Knaus, ‘Australian special forces involved in murder of 39 Afghan civilians, war crimes report alleges’, *The Guardian*, 19 November 2020.

¹²⁸ J. Feng, ‘Chinese Artist Becomes National Hero After Australia War Crimes Tweet Causes Diplomatic Storm’, *Newsweek*, 2 December 2020.

¹²⁹ G. Abbondanza, ‘Australia the ‘good international citizen’? The limits of a traditional middle power’, *Australian Journal of International Affairs* (2020): 1-19.

might continue this interaction, disrupted by one or more phone calls, as they made coffee, got dressed, had breakfast, thought about the day ahead and headed out the door. They would not have seen the Wuheqilin image in these moments, as it would be a few hours yet before Zhao Lijian chose to tweet it.

How the image circulated and its reliance on the Twitter algorithm was an important factor to how it was seen. First posted by the artist Wuheqilin on Weibo, a Chinese social media platform, it only became 'visible' to the Australian diplomatic community following Zhao Lijian's choice to tweet it on Twitter. In the first three hours after Zhao tweeted the image, it had generated more than 2100 interactions and 1400 retweets.¹³⁰ This is particularly important – the Australian diplomatic community has very little engagement with the Weibo platform due to censorship by the Chinese government, and Twitter is banned in China. It was necessary for Zhao Lijian to move the image from one platform to another to harness the Twitter algorithm and its 'trending' visibility, in the hope that Australian diplomats and political leaders would see the image and his tweet – he did not @mention any Australian government accounts or diplomatic representatives directly, so the scope of visibility was conditional on tweet virality. Its visibility was amplified by retweets from an unusually high number of accounts, most with characteristics of fake or bot accounts. Many of these accounts were created in the days prior to Zhao Lijian's tweet and were used only once – to retweet the Australian soldier image. The spike in such accounts signals a likelihood the image was part of an orchestrated campaign to heighten the international visibility of the image, drawing on the Twitter algorithm to ensure the widest possible reach.

The first time someone would have *seen* the Wuheqilin image would have been in their Twitter timeline. Holding their phone, melded into the flesh of their hand and scrolling through the app homepage with their thumb against the screen, it would have been impossible to miss, particularly a tweet by a Chinese government representative well-known for provocative messaging. Zhou Lijian had established a reputation for being confrontational on Twitter, overlapping with a broader 'Wolf Warrior' diplomacy that tended towards the combative, so it is reasonable to assume that Australian diplomats and political leaders were well aware of – and even potentially followed – his Twitter account. But the cropped thumbnail image and its message would have been too small to see in full. Someone would have had to *touch* the tweet with their thumb or finger to see this image in its entirety, including with the overlaid text and quote tweet. Parts of the composite image, namely the child, were quite small so a Twitter user needed to use

¹³⁰ *Al Jazeera*, 'Australia demands China apology over 'repugnant' Twitter post', 30 November 2020, available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/11/30/australia-demands-china-apology-over-repugnant-twitter-post>, accessed on 10 November 2023.

their fingers or thumbs to touch the image and open it fully, and again use their fingers or thumbs, or their hands on the computer mouse, to expand those parts of the image that had more intricate detail. In doing so they would have been confronted with the enlarged composite photo of a child's contorted face, seemingly screaming in pain. It is very likely that, without even realising and almost as an automatic function, this person would have bent their neck even further and raised their hand to their face to better see the image, opening and closing it with their thumb, perhaps sending the tweet as a direct message to their colleagues. They would have spent time going back and forth with the image tweet, as more details would have become visible to them over time: that the flags covered imagined bodies, there were puzzle pieces overlaid on the 'ground' of the image, the uniform and helmet displayed small Australian flags, the soldier in full-booted combat gear while the child's feet were bare. This engagement with the tweet and its image would have contributed to the tweet emerging as a trending topic on Twitter and further enhanced its visibility on the platform. As a result, political importance was accorded to this tweeted image in part because of the higher engagement metrics as calculated through the number of views, retweets, quote tweets or @mentions of Zhao Lijian.¹³¹

It is possible to understand how someone could *feel* about this image. We know this image was affecting: political correspondents in Australia's Parliament House in Canberra reported hearing audible gasps from politicians on the House floor, when the tweeted image was first seen, more than likely on members' smartphones.¹³² Within two hours of the tweet being posted, Morrison had called a press conference where Within 24 hours of the tweet being posted, Morrison had called a press conference where an A4 printout of the tweet was produced to show the 'repugnant' and 'falsified image' (see Image 2).¹³³ Morrison's reaction – stating that 'it is utterly outrageous and cannot be justified on any basis whatsoever, the Chinese Government should be totally ashamed of this post' – suggests seeing the Twitter image produced a particular stress effect, potentially impairing rational political and social decisions based on a more precise and flexible processing of available information as to the origins and reasons behind Zhou Lijian tweeting such an image.¹³⁴

¹³¹ V. Shetty, 'The role of non-elites and eyewitness videos in the visual securitization of Calais asylum seekers', *European Journal of International Security* 7 (2022), pp. 413-434.

¹³² A. Palmer, 'The Man Behind China's Aggressive New Voice', *The New York Times*, 7 July 2021.

¹³³ *BBC News*, 'Australia demands China apologise for posting "repugnant" fake image', 30 November 2020.

¹³⁴ Macias, "News overload".

Image 2. A journalist holds a printout of Zhou Lijian’s tweet following Scott Morrison’s impromptu press conference, 30 November 2020 (Photograph: Mick Tsikas/AAP).

Taken together, the Wuheqilin image is provocative: yet it only visually represented a challenge to diplomatic norms and protocols once it was tweeted by Zhou Lijian, as a foreign representative for the Chinese government. Here we can appreciate the construction of two competing affective communities of sense. One affective community is built around shock, outrage and disgust, uniting Western states such as Australia, New Zealand, France and the United States in reaction to a ‘false’ image. Former New Zealand Prime Minister Jacinda Ardern claimed the image was ‘unfactual’ and that her government had raised concerns about Zhou Lijian’s tweet directly with China.¹³⁵ The United States State Department Deputy Spokesperson Vedant Patel tweeted that the US ‘stand[s] with our Australian partners in calling out @MFA_China for spreading disinformation by fabricating an image of Australian soldiers in Afghanistan. This is a new low, even for the Chinese Communist Party’. The White House National Security Council also lightly trolled China with the tweet ‘Australian wine will be featured at a White House holiday reception this week. Pity vino lovers in China who, due to Beijing’s coercive tariffs on Aussie vintners, will miss out. #AussieAussieAussieOiOiOi!’. The condemnation also connected to

¹³⁵ D. Hurst, ‘France and New Zealand join Australia’s criticism of Chinese government tweet’, *The Guardian*, 1 December 2020.

disbelief in the contravention of diplomatic norms the tweet represented, which generated another layer of emotional response to the image. The French government claimed the tweet was ‘unworthy of diplomatic methods, and an insult to all countries whose armed forces had been engaged in Afghanistan’.¹³⁶ The other affective community unites non-Western states of China and Russia around feelings of shame, contempt and hostility directed at the West and towards Australia in particular.

In the case of the China-Australia Twitter image dispute, the Morrison government could have followed diplomatic norms and expressed grievances privately, or even for China to penalize Zhou Lijian in some way. Instead, the Morrison government was effectively ‘trolled into publicizing its own war crimes’, magnifying deeply shameful military practices that had up until December 2020 received very little international attention.¹³⁷ Morrison’s public demand for an apology as a political performance of outrage further inflamed an already tense situation: following the Twitter dispute, China severed diplomatic contact under the China-Australia Strategic Economic Dialogue, ignored repeated attempts by Australian ministers to contact Beijing, and imposed trade sanctions on exports costing Australia \$23 billion in revenue over the next two years. Rather than dismissing such images as part of the low-politics ‘noise’ of Twitter, we need to better appreciate their role in fomenting conflict in the digital age.

Conclusion

My examination of the role of touch in the emotional dynamics of Twitter illustrates that digital images are central to online debates that have offline political consequences. I argued that the tactile interface between user, device and image produces an affective encounter that contributes to how users feel about social media images. To explore this dynamic, I focused on the Twitter platform to develop an account of social media images as multisensory, involving not just visual but tactile practices. The intertextuality of the visual, tactile and emotional dynamics of Twitter images are important elements of visual social media practices sustaining the strategic representation of identity. Tweeted images do not ‘simply appear or become visible on their own’;¹³⁸ how users interact to (re)shape still and moving images posted on Twitter adds to their affective power. Twitter has its own algorithmic platform logic of circulation that further complicates the image and the emotions connected to it, which in turn influences both how users

¹³⁶ Hurst, ‘France and New Zealand’.

¹³⁷ R. Withers, ‘Everyone Looks Terrible in the Grim China-Australia Twitter War’, *Slate*, 1 December 2020.

¹³⁸ MacKenzie, ‘Why do soldiers swap illicit pictures?’, p.4.

experience the image and how this phenomenon is communicated from one person to another, and from the individual to the group. Twitter images have a different kind of potential to evoke or represent emotions, because these images become an extension of the hand, rendering any barrier between online and offline worlds obsolete through this force of movement. The intersection of seeing and touching Twitter images can draw the user into a space beyond themselves, whereby the visual frames, and is framed by, an emotional experience connecting an individual to a broader collectivity.

Visuals in the digital age are overwhelmingly fixed within material technology (smartphone, desktop) and affective online space (social media platform), which shape the experience of and reaction to digital images. Social media platforms have the potential to provide a space for the orchestration of public feeling in connection to the circulation of images, wherein the digital circulation of affect informs politics and its contestations.¹³⁹ This rich immersive experience simultaneously engages users through physical and affective registers, producing a potent space where visual diplomatic signals are more acute and are driven by the platforms in ways that are not commonly appreciated. Indeed, there is a complex interrelationship between these aspects of the user experience that underpin the utility of social media as sites for the production and contestation of identity.

Here is where several questions emerge for international relations, politics and sociology more broadly. In relation to the materialism of visual politics, we must have a clearer understanding of how diplomats and political leaders use mobile technology to access and interact with social media images and how this is implicated in the way states respond to Twitter images. If technology may provoke people to 'do things they would not have done otherwise', we need a clearer understanding of how users enact technology in practice and what may precipitate such action.¹⁴⁰ Work at the intersection of diplomacy studies and the visual turn in international relations has introduced new insights into the role of social media affordances in conditioning digital diplomacy practice.¹⁴¹ Yet the specific ways in which diplomats and political representatives handle or manage their smartphones as a changeable material interface, and how this embodies and informs deeply

¹³⁹ L. Åhäll, 'Affect as methodology: Feminism and the politics of emotion', *International Political Sociology* 12:1(2018), pp. 36-52; S. Ahmed, 'Affective economies', *Social text* 22:2(2004), pp. 117-139.

¹⁴⁰ V. Pouliot, 'The materials of practice: Nuclear warheads, rhetorical commonplaces and committee meetings in Russian-Atlantic relations', *Cooperation and Conflict* 45(2020), p. 294; R. Adler-Nissen and A. Drieschova, 'Track-change diplomacy: Technology, affordances, and the practice of international negotiations', *International Studies Quarterly* 63(2019), p. 533.

¹⁴¹ Adler-Nissen and A. Drieschova, 'Track-change diplomacy'; Adler-Nissen and Eggeling, 'Blended diplomacy'; J. Cornut, I. Manor and C. Blumenthal, 'WhatsApp with diplomatic practices in Geneva? Diplomats, digital technologies, and adaptation in practice', *International Studies Review* 24:4 (2022): viac047.

held attitudes about communication, technology, interstate relations and norm contestations has yet to be fully explored.¹⁴²

Another pressing question arises in relation to how touch is implicated in the emotional power of images as part of digital disinformation. Images can trigger powerful emotions that move beyond the platform and have implications for offline political engagement. Exposure to misleading or false information is a major challenge for governments around the world, and this is only increasing with the growing prevalence of deceptive and misleading images as part of both authoritarian ‘sharp power’ campaigns and semiotic violence perpetrated by non-state actors.¹⁴³ Further consideration of how the tactile interface between user, device and image produces an affective encounter contributing to how images are seen as ‘truth’ or reflections of reality is necessary to grasp the challenges of digital disinformation and effective attempts to counter it.

Finally, scholars attentive to the power of social media and its visual politics should consider not only the content depicting gender or racial violence circulates on digital platforms such as Twitter, but how the visibility of such content is supported through raced, gendered and ableist platform sharing affordances and the material hardware that allows them to operate.¹⁴⁴

¹⁴² Richardson and L. Hjorth, ‘Mobile media, domestic play and haptic ethnography’.

¹⁴³ E. Hedling, ‘Transforming practices of diplomacy: the European External Action Service and digital disinformation’, *International Affairs* 97:3 (2021), pp. 841-859; M.L. Krook, ‘Semiotic violence against women: Theorizing harms against female politicians’, *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society* 47:2 (2022), pp. 371-397.

¹⁴⁴ E. Morales, ‘Social media and the mediation of everyday violence: A study of Colombian young adults’ experiences’, *New Media & Society* (2024), pp. 1-18; L. Nakamura, ‘Watching white supremacy on digital video platforms: “Screw your optics, I’m going in”’, *Film Quarterly* 73(2019), pp. 19-22; Goggin, ‘Disability and haptic media’.